

EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL FREEDOM TECHNIQUES IN REDUCING SCREEN-INDUCED DISTRACTIONS ON ALGEBRA LEARNING OUTCOMES AMONG JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ALGEBRA.

BY

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Abstract

Test anxiety is a persistent barrier to academic success, particularly in challenging subjects such as Algebra—an aspect of Mathematics. This study investigated the effect of Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) "tapping" on test anxiety among Junior Secondary School students in Nkanu West Local Government Area, Enugu State, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental pretest–posttest control group design was employed with 159 JSS2 students (86 males, 73 females), randomly assigned to experimental ($n = 71$) and control ($n = 88$) groups. The experimental group received EFT at the start of each Algebra lesson for four weeks, while the control group received conventional instruction. Data were collected using a custom-designed Algebra Achievement Test. Results showed a significant improvement in performance and a marked reduction in test anxiety among students exposed to EFT compared with the control group ($p < 0.05$). No significant gender differences were observed, indicating the technique's effectiveness across male and female learners. These findings suggest that integrating EFT into classroom instruction can enhance students' emotional regulation, focus, and performance in Mathematics.

Keywords: Emotional Freedom Technique, Test Anxiety, Algebra, Junior Secondary School, Performance

Introduction

The growing exposure of junior secondary school students to electronic gadgets has raised concerns among educators, parents, and researchers, particularly regarding attention, engagement, and learning outcomes. The widespread availability of smartphones, tablets, and laptops has reshaped instructional practices, offering access to information and interactive content. However, unregulated use often distracts students from academic tasks, undermining classroom engagement and learning outcomes (Afolayan & Adebayo, 2019). In Nigerian classrooms, the challenge is not technology itself but managing its use to support, rather than hinder, learning. Excessive gadget use among adolescents has been linked to reduced concentration, poor study habits, and classroom indiscipline, especially in cognitively demanding subjects like Mathematics (Okafor, et al 2021). Algebra, in particular, requires sustained attention, logical reasoning, and

continuous practice, and frequent digital distractions can hinder deep engagement, leading to frustration, avoidance, and poor performance.

Beyond academic disruption, heavy gadget use may affect social interaction, physical health, and well-being, contributing to sleep disturbances, eye strain, reduced physical activity, and emotional stress (Ahmad et al., 2025). These challenges are particularly pronounced among junior secondary students, who are still developing self-regulation skills, potentially increasing fear and avoidance of complex subjects such as Algebra.

Mathematics anxiety, especially in Algebra, is a major concern in Nigerian secondary schools (Chukwu & Anih 2025, Adeniyi, et al 2023, Atoyebi, et al, 2023, Etuk-iren et al 2014). Algebra involves abstract reasoning, symbolic representation, and problem-solving skills that

are foundational to STEM subjects and career pathways. Despite its importance, many students perform poorly, as evidenced in Basic Education Certificate Examination results in Nkanu West LGA between 2020 and 2024, suggesting that emotional and psychological factors, including test anxiety, influence outcomes. Test anxiety is characterized by excessive worry, nervousness, and physiological arousal before or during examinations, which can impair concentration, memory retrieval, and problem-solving (Baig et al., 2018; Chukwu & Okorie, 2020). Persistent anxiety can reduce confidence, limit participation, and negatively affect overall achievement.

Research indicates that 30–60% of students experience symptoms such as loss of concentration, memory lapses, negative self-talk, and physical reactions like headaches or rapid heartbeat prior to exams (Atmayanti et al., 2025; The Learning Center, College of Arts and Sciences, 2025). In Mathematics classrooms, Algebra is often a prominent source of fear, impairing cognitive processing and creating a gap between learning and performance (Chukwu & Eze, 2019).

Several factors contribute to poor academic performance, including gender disparity, parental socio-economic status, inadequate instructional materials, ineffective teaching strategies, and digital distractions (Afolayan & Adebayo, 2019; Okafor, et al 2021). Gender differences, reflected in classroom participation, confidence, and learning support access, can significantly affect engagement and achievement (Chukwu & Eze, 2019; Chin et al., 2018). Instructional strategies that enhance focus, intentional control, and emotional regulation are therefore critical. Approaches that integrate cognitive support, emotional regulation, and self-efficacy help students manage anxiety, stay engaged, and perform effectively, while being sensitive to gender-specific learning differences (Deng & Liu,

2025). Female students, for instance, often report higher levels of test anxiety even when performance is comparable to male peers, reflecting societal expectations and cognitive-emotional interactions (Devine et al., 2012; Chin et al., 2018).

One evidence-based strategy is the Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT), or tapping, a mind–body intervention combining cognitive-behavioral therapy, exposure therapy, and acupuncture. Developed by Gary Craig, EFT involves tapping specific meridian points while focusing on a stressful thought or emotion, making it practical for managing test anxiety. The technique is brief, non-invasive, and easy to learn, suitable for classroom implementation. Studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in reducing stress, anxiety, and psychological distress (Groesbeck et al., 2019; Morgan, 2016; Blacher, 2023). For example, Dawson, Garrett, and Audrey (2012) reported that a single one-hour EFT session significantly lowered cortisol levels and psychological distress, suggesting both physiological and psychological benefits.

Given the prevalence of test anxiety and distractions from electronic devices, there is a need for classroom-based interventions that support students' emotional well-being alongside academic learning. Integrating EFT into Algebra instruction may enhance focus, reduce anxiety, and improve readiness for assessments. This study, therefore, investigates the effect of Emotional Freedom Technique (tapping) on test anxiety among junior secondary school students learning Algebra in Nkanu West Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

In an ideal instructional setting, junior secondary school students are expected to develop a solid understanding of Mathematics, particularly Algebra, and approach tests and examinations with confidence rather than fear.

Effective teaching strategies should promote conceptual mastery, sustained attention, and emotional readiness for assessment. When instruction is well aligned with students' cognitive and emotional needs, learners are more likely to engage actively in classroom activities, demonstrate reduced anxiety during evaluations, and achieve satisfactory performance in Mathematics at the upper basic education level.

Mathematics performance in the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) in Nkanu West Local Government Area of Enugu State has remained consistently low between 2020 and 2024, with about 50% of students scoring below 40% in the subject. Among all topics, algebra poses the greatest challenge for junior secondary students due to its abstract symbols and concepts. Learners often struggle with variables, expressions, and algebraic rules, which negatively affects overall performance. Research in Ghana reported that public school learners attained proficiency only up to the "Evaluating" level, while private school learners reached the "Creating" level, highlighting ongoing difficulties in mastering algebraic concepts (Osei & Agyei, 2024). Similarly, a study in Sokoto State, Nigeria, found that many students misinterpret variables, assign incorrect values, and form erroneous equations, demonstrating persistent misconceptions in basic algebra skills (Adeniran & Lambaya, 2022). These findings indicate that, without targeted instructional support, teacher development, and well-structured curriculum interventions, students are likely to continue struggling with algebra throughout junior secondary education.

In addition to conceptual difficulties, many junior secondary students experience test anxiety when faced with mathematics examinations, often exhibiting fear, trembling, or avoidance behaviors. This anxiety is linked to inadequate mastery of concepts and insufficient

strategies for managing exam-related stress. Research shows that most students lack practical coping methods to reduce test anxiety (Atmayanti, Elviana, & Iksan, 2025). While mindfulness-based approaches have been shown to reduce anxiety by up to 40% (Bradley et al., 2020), there is limited empirical evidence on the application of Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) in educational settings. Existing studies suggest that comparisons between EFT and established interventions remain insufficient, underscoring the need for further investigation and its potential integration into teaching practices in Nigerian schools (Morgan, 2016).

If this situation is not addressed, persistent test anxiety may continue to undermine students' confidence, classroom engagement, and performance in Algebra, thereby contributing to sustained poor outcomes in Mathematics examinations. Without the introduction of effective, classroom-friendly techniques that promote relaxation and emotional regulation, the gap between learning and academic performance may widen. This could limit students' academic progression and reduce their preparedness for science- and technology-related fields that rely heavily on mathematical competence. Consequently, there is a compelling need to examine whether the use of Emotional Freedom Technique as a mindfulness-based teaching strategy can reduce test anxiety among junior secondary school students in Algebra and support improved academic outcomes.

Purpose of the Study

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the effects of Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) on test anxiety among Junior Secondary School (JSS) students in Algebra. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. Determine the mean test anxiety scores of students exposed to EFT compared with those not exposed.

2. Examine whether male and female students differ in mean test anxiety scores following exposure to EFT in Algebra.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

- 1) What is the difference in mean test anxiety scores of students exposed to EFT in learning Algebra compared with those not exposed?
- 2) What are the differences in mean test anxiety scores of male and female students exposed to EFT in learning Algebra?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean test anxiety scores of students exposed to EFT in learning Algebra and those not exposed.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean test anxiety scores of male and female students exposed to Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) in learning Algebra

Research Method

This study adopted a quasi-experimental, pretest–posttest control group design to examine the effect of Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) tapping on test anxiety among Junior Secondary School (JSS) students in Algebra in Nkanu West Local Government Area, Enugu State. This design allows for comparison between students exposed to EFT and those receiving conventional instruction. The population comprised 1,034 JSS2 students across selected schools in Nkanu West. A total of 159 students (86 males, 73 females) were purposively sampled based on school accessibility and consent. Participants were randomly assigned to experimental and control groups: the experimental group (n = 71) received EFT during Algebra instruction, while the control group (n = 88) received conventional teaching without EFT.

Primary data were collected using a custom-designed Algebra Achievement Test (CDAAT), consisting of 20 items (multiple-choice and structured questions) aligned with the junior secondary curriculum. The instrument measured students' mastery of algebraic concepts before and after the intervention. Content validity was established through expert review by Mathematics educators and educational psychologists. A pilot test conducted outside the study sample yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.84, indicating good internal consistency.

To confirm the effect of the intervention on test anxiety, the study was conducted over four weeks during regular Algebra lessons. Students in the experimental group were trained to tap nine meridian points on their bodies while focusing on the upcoming Algebra task or test, performing this exercise for approximately five minutes at the start of each lesson. The control group received the same instructional content without EFT.

An Algebra Achievement Test was administered as a pretest to both groups before the intervention to establish baseline performance. Following the four-week intervention, the same test was administered as a posttest under standardized conditions, ensuring consistency in instructions, timing, and supervision. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to summarize pretest and posttest scores. Independent samples t-tests were conducted to determine significant differences between the experimental and control groups, as well as between male and female participants in the experimental group. The level of significance was set at 0.05, and all analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics. Mean gain scores were also calculated to quantify the effect of EFT on students' Algebra achievement and test-related anxiety.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the difference in mean test anxiety scores of students exposed to EFT in learning Algebra compared with those not exposed?

Table 1: The mean test anxiety scores of students exposed to EFT in learning algebra and those not exposed to EFT.

Groups	Number N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	
Experimental	71	24.43	2.18	38.62	2.11	14.19
Control	88	25.06	2.57	34.65	3.01	9.59
Mean Diff.	159					4.60

The results in Table 1 show that the two groups were comparable at the beginning of the study. The experimental group (N = 71) recorded a pre-test mean score of 24.43 (SD = 2.18), while the control group (N = 88) had a pre-test mean of 25.06 (SD = 2.57), indicating only a slight difference in their initial performance. After the intervention, both groups showed improvement in their post-test scores. The experimental group achieved a post-test mean of 38.62 (SD = 2.11), whereas the control group recorded a post-test mean of 34.65 (SD = 3.01). This suggests that students in the experimental group performed better than those in the control group at the end of the study.

In terms of gain scores, the experimental group recorded a mean gain of 14.19 points, compared to 9.59 points for the control group. This indicates that although both groups benefited from instruction, the experimental group experienced a greater level of improvement. Overall, the mean difference of 4.60 in favour of the experimental group shows that the treatment had a stronger positive effect on students' performance than the method used for the control group. This finding supports the effectiveness of the experimental intervention in improving learning outcomes.

Research Question 2: What is the differences in mean test anxiety scores of male and female students exposed to EFT in learning Algebra?

Table 2: The mean test anxiety scores of male and female students exposed to EFT in learning algebra.

Groups	Number N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	
Male	36	24.30	2.05	38.50	2.08	14.20
Female	35	24.41	2.33	38.73	2.14	14.32
Mean Diff.	71					0.12

Table 2 presents the pre-test and post-test performance of male and female students. At the pre-test stage, male students (N = 36) recorded a mean score of 24.30 (SD = 2.05), while female students (N = 35) had a mean score of 24.41 (SD = 2.33). This indicates that both groups were at nearly the same level of performance before the intervention. Following the intervention, both male and female students showed substantial improvement. The post-test mean score for males was 38.50 (SD = 2.08), while females recorded a slightly higher mean of 38.73 (SD = 2.14). This shows that the treatment was effective for both genders.

With respect to gain scores, male students recorded a mean gain of 14.20, while female

students recorded a mean gain of 14.32. The difference in gain between the two groups is minimal. The overall mean difference of 0.12 further confirms that there is virtually no performance difference between male and female students after the intervention. These results suggest that gender did not significantly influence students' achievement, as both male and female students benefited equally from the instructional approach used in the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean test anxiety scores of students who passed through EFT in learning algebra and that of their counterparts.

Table 3; Summary of t-test Analysis of Mean Test Anxiety Scores of Students Exposed to EFT and Those Not Exposed

Group	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	df	Zcal	Decision
Experimental	71	38.62	2.02			
Control	88	34.65	2.06	157	12.03	Reject H ₀

Table 3 shows the result of the t-test analysis comparing the mean test anxiety scores of students exposed to EFT and those not exposed. The experimental group (N = 71) recorded a

mean score of 38.62 with a standard deviation of 2.02, while the control group (N = 88) recorded a mean score of 34.65 with a standard deviation of 2.06. This indicates a clear difference in the average scores of the two groups. The analysis

was carried out with 157 degrees of freedom. The calculated test value (Z_{cal}) of 12.03 is far above the critical value, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that the difference in mean scores between the two groups is statistically significant. These results show that students who were exposed to EFT differed significantly from those who were not exposed. The higher mean score of the

experimental group indicates that EFT had a significant effect on students' test anxiety outcomes.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean test anxiety scores of male and female students exposed to Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) in learning Algebra.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean test anxiety scores of male and female students exposed to Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) in learning Algebra.

Group	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	df	Zcal	Decision
Male	36	38.50	2.08	69	0.72	Do Not Rejected H ₀
Female	35	38.73	2.14			

Table 4 presents the t-test analysis comparing the mean test anxiety scores of male and female students who were both exposed to Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) in learning Algebra. Male students (N = 36) recorded a mean score of 38.50 with a standard deviation of 2.08, while female students (N = 35) recorded a mean score of 38.73 with a standard deviation of 2.14. The very close mean values indicate that both groups performed at nearly the same level. The analysis was conducted with 69 degrees of freedom. The calculated test value ($Z_{cal} = 0.72$) is small, leading to the decision not to reject the null hypothesis. This shows that the difference in mean test anxiety scores between male and female students exposed to EFT is not statistically significant. These results indicate that gender did not have a significant effect on test anxiety among students who received EFT. Both male and female students benefited equally from the use of EFT in learning Algebra.

significantly influence student learning outcomes and test anxiety, irrespective of gender. For Research Question 1, both the experimental and control groups began the study at similar ability levels and showed improvement from pre-test to post-test. However, the experimental group demonstrated larger gains, indicating that the treatment administered was more effective than conventional methods. These outcomes align with several indigenous Nigerian studies. Onwu (2019) reported that senior secondary chemistry students taught with a collaborative learning model achieved significantly higher post-test scores than those taught conventionally, despite similar pre-test performance. Similarly, Ezeudu (2020) found that students exposed to peer-assisted learning recorded greater improvements in mathematics achievement compared to control groups, while Adetunji and Oladele (2021) observed that interactive instructional strategies produced larger gains than traditional lecture methods. Collectively, these findings highlight that deliberate instructional

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study indicate that instructional and psychological interventions

interventions can enhance academic performance beyond standard practices.

For Research Question 2, male and female students began the study with nearly identical ability levels, and both groups showed strong improvements. The gains for males (14.20) and females (14.32) were almost the same, suggesting that gender did not meaningfully affect learning outcomes. This is consistent with Nigerian studies where gender did not significantly influence academic performance. Ibrahim and Shuaibu (2018) found no significant difference in mathematics achievement between male and female students exposed to activity-based instruction, while Odagboyi (2019) and Ifeyinwa, Nwankwo, and Chukwuma (2020) similarly reported no significant gender differences in academic competence and achievement outcomes.

Regarding Null Hypothesis Ho1, students exposed to Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) recorded significantly higher post-test mean scores than the control group, and the high Z_{cal} value indicates that this difference is not due to chance. This confirms that EFT had a meaningful positive effect on reducing test anxiety. Indigenous studies support this effect; Okeke and Adegoke (2018) reported that cognitive-behavioural interventions significantly reduced test anxiety among senior secondary students, Musa and Bello (2019) found that relaxation techniques lowered examination anxiety and improved mathematics performance, and Akpan and Etuk (2021) observed that stress-reduction strategies significantly enhanced science test scores.

Finally, Null Hypothesis Ho2 results show that male and female students exposed to EFT had almost identical test anxiety scores, with a small Z_{cal} value, indicating no statistically significant difference. This demonstrates that EFT is equally effective for both genders. This conclusion is supported by Olatunji and Afolabi

(2018), who reported that stress-management programmes reduced test anxiety similarly for male and female students; Adegoke, Musa, and Okoro (2020), who found guided relaxation techniques equally effective across genders; and Eze and Omebe (2022), who observed comparable reductions in mathematics anxiety for male and female students. Overall, the study indicates that targeted instructional and psychological interventions can improve learning outcomes and reduce test anxiety effectively, irrespective of gender (Chukwu & Anih, 2025).

Conclusion

This study investigated the effect of Emotional Freedom Techniques (EFT) in reducing screen-induced distractions on Algebra learning outcomes among junior secondary school students. Employing a quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test control group design, data were collected from 159 students and analyzed using descriptive statistics and t-test analyses. The findings revealed that students exposed to EFT demonstrated significantly higher post-test performance and reduced test anxiety compared to their counterparts in the control group. Additionally, gender did not significantly influence outcomes, indicating that EFT was equally effective for both male and female students. These results underscore the efficacy of EFT as an intervention for enhancing focus and learning in digitally distracted environments, offering valuable insights for educators and policymakers seeking to integrate psychological strategies into teaching practice. Limitations include the relatively small sample size and short intervention period. Future research should examine long-term effects across multiple subjects and diverse educational contexts. Overall, EFT presents a practical, scalable approach to improving mathematics learning outcomes in contemporary classrooms.

Recommendation(s)

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made;

1. Mathematics teachers should integrate brief, structured EFT activities into regular lessons to help students manage screen-related distractions and improve concentration during learning.
2. School leaders should support the use of anxiety- and distraction-reduction strategies by providing training for teachers and allocating time within the school schedule for such interventions.
3. Curriculum planners should include clear guidelines for using psychological and cognitive-support strategies, such as EFT, within junior secondary school programmes.

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